

On the near pseudo Smarandache function

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the near pseudo Smarandache function $K(n)$ is defined as $K(n) = m = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + k$, where k is the smallest positive integer such that n divides m . The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the calculating problem of an infinite series involving the near pseudo Smarandache function $K(n)$, and give an exact calculating formula.

Keywords Near pseudo Smarandache function, infinite series, exact calculating formula.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , the near pseudo Smarandache function $K(n)$ is defined as follows:

$$K(n) = m,$$

where $m = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + k$, and k is the smallest positive integer such that n divides m .

The first few values of $K(n)$ are $K(1) = 2$, $K(2) = 4$, $K(3) = 9$, $K(4) = 12$, $K(5) = 20$, $K(6) = 24$, $K(7) = 35$, $K(8) = 40$, $K(9) = 54$, $K(10) = 50$, $K(11) = 77$, $K(12) = 84$, $K(13) = 104$, $K(14) = 112$, $K(15) = 135$, \dots . This function was introduced by A.W.Vyawahare and K.M.Purohit in [1], where they studied the elementary properties of $K(n)$, and obtained a series interesting results. For example, they proved that 2 and 3 are the only solutions of $K(n) = n^2$; If $a, b > 5$, then $K(a \cdot b) > K(a) \cdot K(b)$; If $a > 5$, then for all positive integer n , $K(a^n) > n \cdot K(a)$; The Fibonacci numbers and the Lucas numbers do not exist in the sequence $\{K(n)\}$; Let C be the continued fraction of the sequence $\{K(n)\}$, then C is convergent and $2 < C < 3$; $K(2^n - 1) + 1$ is a triangular number; The series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(n)}$ is convergent. The other contents related to the near pseudo Smarandache function can also be found in references [2], [3] and [4].

In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the calculating problem of the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^s(n)}, \quad (1)$$

and give an exact calculating formula for (1). That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. For any real number $s > \frac{1}{2}$, the series (1) is convergent, and

$$(a) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(n)} = \frac{2}{3} \ln 2 + \frac{5}{6};$$

$$(b) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^2(n)} = \frac{11}{108} \cdot \pi^2 - \frac{22 + 2 \ln 2}{27}.$$

In fact for any positive integer s , using our method we can give an exact calculating formula for (1), but the calculation is very complicate if s is large enough.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall prove our theorem directly. In fact for any positive integer n , it is easily to deduce that $K(n) = \frac{n(n+3)}{2}$ if n is odd and $K(n) = \frac{n(n+2)}{2}$ if n is even. So from this properties we may immediately get

$$\frac{n^2}{2} < K(n) < \frac{(n+3)^2}{2},$$

or

$$\frac{1}{(n+3)^{2s}} \ll \frac{1}{K^s(n)} \ll \frac{1}{n^{2s}}.$$

So the series (1) is convergent if $s > \frac{1}{2}$.

Now from the properties of $K(n)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(2n-1)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(2n)} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)(n+1)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2n(n+1)} \\ &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2n-1} - \frac{1}{2n+2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1} \right) \\ &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{2n-1} - \sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{2n+2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \\ &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{n \leq 2N} \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{2N+2} + \frac{1}{2} - \sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Note that for any $N > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula (See Theorem 3.2 of [5])

$$\sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{n} = \ln N + \gamma + O\left(\frac{1}{N}\right), \quad (3)$$

where γ is the Euler constant.

Combining (2) and (3) we may immediately obtain

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K(n)} = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln(2N) + \gamma + \frac{1}{2} - \ln N - \gamma + O\left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \right] + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{2}{3} \ln 2 + \frac{5}{6}.$$

This completes the proof of (a) in Theorem.

Now we prove (b) in Theorem. From the definition and properties of $K(n)$ we also have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^2(n)} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^2(2n-1)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^2(2n)} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^2(n+1)^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^2(n+1)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Note that the identities

$$\frac{1}{(2n-1)^2(n+1)^2} = \frac{2}{27} \left(\frac{1}{2n+2} - \frac{1}{2n-1} \right) + \frac{1}{9} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^2} + \frac{1}{9} \frac{1}{(2n+2)^2}, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{n^2(n+1)^2} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{8} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+1)^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} - 1. \quad (7)$$

From (3), (4), (5), (6) and (7) we may deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{K^2(n)} &= \frac{2}{27} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2n+2} - \frac{1}{2n-1} \right) + \frac{1}{9} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{(2n-1)^2} + \frac{1}{(2n+2)^2} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{2}{27} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[\sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{2n+2} - \sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{2n-1} \right] + \frac{\pi^2}{72} + \frac{\pi^2}{216} - \frac{1}{36} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[\sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{n+1} - \sum_{n \leq N} \frac{1}{n} \right] + \frac{\pi^2}{24} + \frac{\pi^2}{24} - \frac{1}{4} \\ &= \frac{2}{27} \cdot \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[-\frac{1}{2} + \ln N - \ln(2N) + O\left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \right] + \frac{\pi^2}{54} - \frac{1}{36} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\pi^2}{12} - \frac{1}{4} \\ &= \frac{11}{108} \cdot \pi^2 - \frac{22 + 2 \ln 2}{27}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of (b) in Theorem.

References

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